

Physical Models of Quantum Music

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Abstract. *Music operates rather directly on the senses, and aesthetic notions such as a harmonious composition of an element being analyzed in a rather rigid form, compared to other arts.*

An extension of the mathematical structure of music into a quantum form- in as much as it would offer any aesthetic value- would either enable a new form of aesthetic experience or rather lead to a revision in our current notions of music and sound, to allow the penetration of quantum phenomena to the currently excluded realm of macroscopic acoustics.

In this article we shall consider two models for quantum music, to derive the conditions under which these could be distinguished from purely classical music, and to the extent to which it could offer any aesthetic value. In this context, we would offer a novel practical implementation to a quantum sound modulator- feasible on today's quantum computation resources.

1 Introduction

In what comes, we would analyze different systems of sound that obey quantum mechanisms (at least in some of their dynamics) and produce what we will refer to as quantum music. Those quantum systems should be discriminated by a human observer from an equivalent physical system of sound that obeys only classical mechanics.

The discrimination procedure would be held by a human listener, who should in principle be able to report different sounds from the two equivalent systems. A more subtle distinction- with respect to the aesthetic value given by the listener- would be also considered.

Since a detailed theory of quantum acoustics is far from having a consensus, the different quantum systems of sound proposed will be grounded on different assumptions, both over the physical process to take place in the human auditorial system and the medium that carry the sound wave. The assumptions would be further extended to the extent where a different aesthetic experience would be reported.

The structure of the article would be the following. Chapter 2 would discuss the representation of music in quantum states, along with a brief introduction to the relevant elements of quantum theory. Chapter 3 would discuss the quantum synthesizer. Chapter 4 the quantum synthesizer with quantum speakers. Both chapters would distinguish the models that can claim to be distinguished from any purely classical music. Chapter 5 would offer a summary of those and a further discussion of the possible aesthetic value of each model. Chapter 6 would introduce the quantum uncertainty modulator, in the light of the conclusions of chapter 5. Chapter 7 a short summary of the article and it's approach towards the construction of quantum music.

2 Quantum sound

2.1 Quantizing a Piano

Any expansion of a certain physical phenomenon into an appropriate quantum mechanical representation requires an initial set of presumably fundamental states. These states must be distinguishable from one another under a given measurement.

Since one of the motives is the expansion of musicology to contain quantum relations, we shall first follow Svozil and Putz's work, and choose a set of states with respect to the Chromatic scale as realized in a piano [1].

Figure 1: different notes in the C major scale. Taken from [1]

A given sound would thus be described as by two quantum observables- note and octave- and their equivalent type of measurements.¹ Assuming that a tone could be fully determined², The result of performing the two measurements must be in a certain state:

1. $|\Psi_{sound}\rangle = |n\rangle|O\rangle = |n, O\rangle$

¹ We shall omit from this article any mathematical constrains imposed on a quantum basis and observable, see [2] for more elaborated derivation of these notions.

² I.E that the note and octave observables commute [1]

Where n is the note and must belong to each of 7 options and O is the octave and must belong to one out of 8 options.

The state prior to measurement can be in a superposition and so composed of several possible notes and octaves. Upon measurement, the superposition state would collapse into one of the possibilities composing it.³

The state of a single sound could be entangled into other sounds, where entanglement between states assures that measuring the state of one key would lead to a measurement of the other.

To make these phenomena distinguished from classical acoustic wave mechanics, we make further assumptions regarding our general way to quantize sound. Let's say that each elementary system of sound is a result of pressing one piano key. A superposition in each sound is therefore the result of a piano key hitting a string in few different places at once. Entanglement would be the correlation of the uncertain (super positioned) state of two sounds to one another.

Assuming further that the measurement apparatus for note and octave is located in some conscious part of the human auditorial system- the super position state is a state of a sound only before noticed by the human listener. Respectively, entanglement would be the way few sounds are orchestrated in a melody in such a way, that if one concrete sound is noticed, also the others become explicit.

These assumptions are made for purely explanatory reason and would be revised for more plausible ones in the following chapters.

2.2 quantizing frequency

In expanding classical sound into QM states, one need not confine himself to a discrete set of possible measurement outcomes. Also, the continues variable of sound frequency can be selected, given that a measurement of frequency exist that satisfies quantum principles [3]. Mainly, that once measured a distinct sound would hold a certain frequency, regardless of any superposition of frequencies in which he was prior to measurement.

When stating a continuous observable in Quantum mechanics, one should consider the uncertainty relation to which this observable would obey, with respect to another observable with which it doesn't commute.

The prime example of such a relation is the location-momentum, dictating a maximum accuracy for joint

location and momentum determination. A similar relation holds for time and energy relation [4]:

$$2. \quad \Delta T \Delta E \geq \frac{1}{2} \hbar$$

Where \hbar is the plank constant, which is at the core of the quantization of every phenomenon governed by quantum principles.

Starting with the quantization of the light wave into the quantized photon energies- where the fundamental energy quanta is proportional to the frequency of the wave ($E \propto \hbar f$)[1], One can hope to extend the quantization of light wave similarly in sound waves, and thus end up with a certain discrete energy. Out of similar considerations, Gabor attempted to quantize sound by identifying the frequency of a sound as a quantum observable [5]. In his approach, continuous frequency is no more than an ideal scenario. In practice, every measurement of a sound is restricted to a certain time window, which, as a result of this finite sampling, would be bound to a maximum frequency accuracy. Led by this intuition, he offered an extension to the well-known Fourier transform, that accounts for the non-vanishing minimum quanta of time and frequency accuracy.

Similarly, to our derivation of the note and orchestra observables in the previous chapter, also Gabor choice of observable, was not accounted by observation of an actual measurement obeying quantum principles,⁴ but rather look for such measurements in human auditorial perception.

Figure 2: Gabor's quantized version of the Fourier transform. Taken from [5]

2.3 quantizing lattice vibration modes

Another approach, based on the same incentive to find the acoustical correlation to quantized light, is the phonon

³ We ignore any interpretation for the QM measurement that denies the actual collapse of the superposition, for the additional complexity to the notion of quantum computation (which will be required in chapter 3). Among them the famous many worlds interpretation. See [3] for the relation of this interpretation to quantum computation.

⁴ For the sake of completeness, we highlight the implicit but clear

distinction between a quantum measurement and that of an abstract measurement- even one done on a physical state that is a statistical mixture and therefore could also yield random results- only (two non-commuting) quantum measurements can violate bell inequality. See introduction of [6] for an elaborated account.

approach. Just like the photon, a phonon is the quanta of energy whose energy is quantized with respect to the frequency of the wave it represents (based on Plank law). But here, the energy is the vibrational energy oscillating the structure of the medium where the phonon “wave” propagates. A convenient illustration of the oscillations is that of a steady wave.

Figure 3: phonons propagate through the molecular structure of a solid. Credit: Sean Kelley/NIST

As opposed to our previous considerations, the phonon energy (frequency) can be measured [7] by a quantum measurement of a defined physical system (and requires no association to the auditorial perception structure), such measurements had empirically verified quantum interference [8], transfer of quantum information [9], and entanglement in macroscopic scale (but still in scale of only μM) which gave the system involved the extravagant name of a quantum drum [10].

This approach to quantizing sound, as promised as it seems in current research, still suffers from a great step back, which is its reliance on a structured medium whose vibrational modes identify the energy of the phonon⁵. Visually, a vibration of the structure that resembles that of an invisible string connecting the particles composing the structure. This particle can be in a super position of location and speed, and therefore the string could vibrate in few different ways simultaneously. It is for this reason that generalizing the notion of phonon to quantize sound waves in air- a medium with chaotic distribution of particles between which a visual representation as that of the string would not fit- has yet to be done.

Current attempts to extend the phonon validity are done on liquid, and as opposed to the collective movement of phonons in solid- that is realized in a string-like movement between molecules in the solid- the collective movement to carry the phonons is based on the repeating collisions of the liquid molecules [12]. Though these molecules are kept in an extremely low temperature, and as such one can try to imagine the inherently random movement governing these collisions as a sort of wave propagation, such loose use indicates a more ontological foundation accepted to the phonon. One that extends beyond his primal definition as a quasi-particle signifying

oscillations in structured solid.

Even if phonons would be proven applicable as some vibrational mode of air in normal atmosphere conditions, propagating quantum sound waves are generally vulnerable to decoherence- since interact not only with charged particles (like photons) but with all the molecules it vibrates in the medium through which it passes. The cost of decoherence is anyway equivalent to reducing the sound wave phenomena back into classical mechanics. As well, the single-to-noise ratio of quantum sound waves will be worse than its electromagnetic counterpart, since its frequency is lower.

To conclude this chapter, we will highlight one possible relation between quantum behavior and classical wave mechanics. Though the following is based on an experiment done on light waves, we would present it to later use it as a recipe for similar mechanisms in sound waves.

In a recent article [13], The phenomena of a particle passing through a matter and emitting light by its movement was examined. If one assumes the particle passing and emitting radiation- in this case, an electron- is in a classical state, the light it would emit is expected to be temporally (I.E classically) coherent. In The quantum picture of the same phenomena, coherence light is the result of the emission only in certain cases, with respect to the uncertainty of momentum (and therefore location) satisfied by the electron. Roughly speaking, too large of certainty in the momentum of the electron- as could be done by a fine measurement of its momentum, or simply by decoherence of its state, the bigger the uncertainty of the emitted light, and therefore the loss of the temporal coherence of the emitted light. In fact, the Authors go as far as declaring:

“...represents a rather deep conclusion: It demonstrates how the well-known classical wave interference can only be generated by a quantum particle that has a certain momentum uncertainty.”

Utilizing a similar mechanism for the interference of sound waves would require more than an appropriate quantization of sound waves in the air. One needs to account for the previously mentioned limitations of the low frequency/energy of sound waves [13]. Still, in the next chapters, we would revisit this possible intimate relation between classical and quantum waves.

⁵ thus phonons were observed mainly in solids, though exceptions could

be found [11]

Figure 4: Interference pattern of light for (a) coherent and (b) decoherent emitter of light. Taken from [13].

3 The quantum synthesizer

The quantum synthesizer is defined as a close quantum system, that can perform quantum coherent evolution inside of it, but output only classical states- albeit perform perfect measurement over the evolved states. The input could be thought of as a classical set of sounds, undergoing a certain quantum process- evolving into a superposition or entangling with preceding sounds- and later fed to conventional speakers.

Since the speakers can only process classical input (set of voltages fitting to a set of distinct sounds), and therefore would anyway perform a measurement over the output of the synthesizer and collapse it to a classical state, it is natural to assume that a more controlled measurement would be done beforehand by the quantum synthesizer itself, who would feed the classical results of the measurement into the speaker.

Figure 5: Abstract model of a general quantum synthesizer

For the sake of clarification, we would write explicitly the state to which the quantum computer evolves the input to, for simplicity we assume only two input and output sounds:

$$3. |\Psi_{sound}(t = t2)\rangle = \sum_{n,m} a_{n,m} |n\rangle_{sound 1} |m\rangle_{sound 2}$$

where the summation over n,m runs over all options in a given basis of sound. After measurement the two sounds system would collapse into a certain state, let's say $|n'\rangle|m'\rangle$.

This model is no different from that of the universal quantum computer. In fact, though the processing of the input inside the synthesizer was initially referred to as operating on a sound state, no superposition of sound takes

⁶ though his lack of knowledge with respect to the actual entanglement of his system would make his ability to distinct his "analog" results

place. The sound is merely symbolized by quantum bits of information. Of the three possibilities we considered- representation of sound through notes and octaves, frequencies discretized by the sensitivity threshold of the human ear, or an actual phonon state (operating somewhat like an analog modulator of frequencies) we expect to have the same scope of algorithms. Prioritizing one of the representations- or any other- would stem only from the convenience of finding an appropriate algorithm for a required task.

A composer who would wish to simply entangle some of the different notes in a musical piece- and explore the different random compositions that could be output by the measurement, would use the first representation.

A musician with a more mathematical approach who wish to create super-position of fifths would probably find the explicit representation of the sound frequencies to be more appealing.

And a producer who would wish to sample the random noise produced from measurements of an actual sound wave- and not any of his ideal realizations- might rather be using the third phonon-based representation.⁶

Therefore, the ability to discriminate the product of a quantum synthesizer from any classical equivalent is strongly related to the question of quantum computation superiority. It is fair to assume that once the quantum Shor algorithm would be accessible - which is theoretically proven to offer exponential speed up in performing Fourier transform [15]- quantum computing would be vastly used for sound modulation of many sorts.

4 Quantum synthesizer with quantum speakers

A quantum synthesizer with a quantum speaker would be defined equivalently to the normal quantum synthesizer, with a single addition- no measurement is done by the quantum synthesizer itself, and the end of the quantum computation- which ideally is in a pure quantum state, get entangled with a quantum speaker- specifically with its vibrational degrees of freedom.

Figure 6: Abstract model of a quantum synthesizer with quantum speaker

Given that we have full control over the interaction- and therefore over the entanglement- of the quantum speaker's modes, and assuming for now that we trust our understanding of the further entanglement of the quantum speakers to the air, we can omit the state of the quantum computer from our consideration.⁷

from any other random distribution [15]

⁷ Mathematically speaking, with knowledge of the diagonal basis of the

Further assuming -for simplicity only- that both the state of the quantum speaker can be represented by a single phonon, we can write the following state at the end of the interaction of the speaker and the air:

$$4. |\Psi_{sound}(t = t3)\rangle = \sum_i e_i |i\rangle_{phonon} |i\rangle_{air}$$

Where i runs over all possible energy level of the phonon, e_i is one of the energy levels and $|i\rangle_{air}$ represent a certain state of the air. This state in principle can be composed of more degrees of freedom but those participating in the propagation of sound wave in air.

Upon arriving at the ear- which we assume to be sensitive only to degrees of freedom representing the sound wave in the air- only the sound degrees of freedom are measured, while the others are traced out, resulting in decoherence of the pure state in equation 4. Beyond a certain level of decoherence, what the ear would measure would anyway be in a mixture state, and there is seemingly no difference between the quantum synthesizer of the last chapter and this one. Where the simple synthesizer dropped any additional quantum information in the point of measurement, the one with quantum speakers dropped it in the decoherence of air.

Revisiting the concluding remark of Chapter 3, this case is almost equivalent to the electrons that emits photons. The emitter now is the speaker phonon, and the emitted energy is the sound wave propagating in air- in as much as it could be quantized. Given that it could be realized as a quantum state (along with the other conditions given in [14]), we might expect some notion of classical interference in the sound wave in air, to be dependent on the uncertainty determined in the speaker. Therefore, an over-determination of the state of the speaker by the quantum computer would yield a high uncertainty relation in the air sound wave, which will destroy its classical interference.

A difference from non-quantum music could be achieved by destroying the interference by improper setting of the state of the quantum speaker (by over-determination of one of the sound characters, where its uncertainty relation to another character of sound would push this one to ambiguity).

Note that in this case the measurement of the listener is analyzed purely classically, and the interference observed by the listener should be of a classical form. In the case where coherence is maintained, the state upon arriving at the ear is of the same form as equation 4. Let's choose an explicit quantum state:

$$5. \Psi_{sound}(t = t3) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} |G, 3\rangle_{phonon} |G, 3\rangle_{air} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} |G, 5\rangle_{phonon} |G, 5\rangle_{air}$$

speaker-air interaction, one can choose a quantum computer speaker interaction whose Schmidt decomposition yields the same basis. In such constellation, the quantum computer degrees of

Where the state of the phonon and air were described for convenience in the note and octave basis. let's assume further that the ear contains the same basis of states, and that it entangles to the sound in a manner that avoids intervening with the information it's trying to perceive:

$$6. \Psi_{sound}(t = t4) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} |G, 3\rangle_{phonon} |G, 3\rangle_{air} |Hearing G, 3\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} |G, 5\rangle_{phonon} |G, 5\rangle_{air} |Hearing G, 5\rangle$$

And after measurement:

$$7. \Psi_{sound}(t = t5) = |G, 3\rangle_{phonon} |G, 3\rangle_{air} |Hearing G, 3\rangle \text{ or } |G, 5\rangle_{phonon} |G, 5\rangle_{air} |Hearing G, 5\rangle$$

In order to avoid the peculiar consequence of equation 6- that for some time two sounds are being heard simultaneously, one can assume the time of the interaction between the sound wave and the ear to be 0, such that the measurement happens instantly.

In such cases, different but identical listeners can report hearing different sounds, with respect to their own measurement outcome.

5 Aesthetical distinction

In this section, we shall examine briefly each of the physical models that were assumed to be distinct from purely classical music. We wish to see if- under the physical conditions allowing distinction- we can hope for aesthetic value arising from these models. We will argue that the success of these models- if occurs- is intimately related to the existence of quantum phenomena in current experience of sound. We will also discuss briefly the advantage in such relation- applying quantum phenomenology on our current understanding of music. This underline conclusion is in the core of the proposed algorithm in the next section- which is inspired by one of these physical realizations.

We begin with what seems as the most promising architecture of quantum music that is inherently different than classical one- that of a quantum synthesizer with a quantum speaker under perfect coherence and measurement. This system offers a peculiar nature different than our experience of a classical sound, but it seems fair to assume that beyond the entertaining value of a music hall full of listeners hearing different melodies, no unique harmony or beauty should be expected to arise from such constellation.

freedom can be traced out without decohering the remained system. For a more careful derivation see [16]

Still, In the case where an additional aesthetic value is to be reported, we would consider as a prominent explanation a non-vanishing duration of interaction between the sound and the ear, such that before measurement, there is an interval where a richer audial experience occurs- and two sounds get entangled to the audial system at the same time. After which the state would collapse, and a distinct sound could be explicitly reported.

The existence of such mechanism- performing quantum sensing of audial input- suggests that quantum audial waves already exist in nature, around which the sensitivity of the human ear naturally evolved. In this case, the aesthetic value of a musical piece could not be derived directly from the sets of notes reported by the listener- as ideal as his observation is- but is at least partially governed by a (quantum) interaction with the quantum sound, from which the conscious mind is excluded.

It is of such accounts that the symbiosis of quantum and arts is so appealing, for it give a physical ground to the belief that aesthetic perception is different than objective one [17], such that the objective image constructed via perception (a concrete set of frequency symbolized by a notes sheet) does not exhaust the content from which the aesthetic value is derived. In other words, the mathematical relation between the frequencies is not enough to know which combination of notes will complement each other, since they are dependent on the quantum states of the notes before collapsing.

Similar accounts could be made for the other physical realization for quantum music. Regarding our second model- that of a quantum synthesizer with a quantum speaker under decoherence, who's distinguishability was dependent on a relation between quantum uncertainty and classical interference phenomena.

It is rather direct to assume that the success of such machine would encourage research on the relation between interference patterns (or more broadly- complementing sounds) in classical sound to the uncertainty in any given musical instrument- from tuning accuracy, to the uncertainty of produced sound with respect to the size of a finger, to the relation to time sampling (as postulated by Gabor in the Heisenberg-Gabor limit[18]).

Uncertainty in classical theories tend to be accounted as a meaningless feature. A state of ignorance that carry no information. Not so with the quantum uncertainty- only through which the quantum state can act in its non classical fashion- teleporting wave information that though impenetrable,⁸ its reality could not be ignored.⁹

Through accepting Quantum uncertainty in music theory, phenomena such as over-determination would have to be taken as causing actual effect on the produced sound. Not a merely arbitrary flues of our reliance on Fourier decomposition, but an inevitable nature of sound production. And thus, to shed light on a sort of delicacy required to

produce a harmony, a delicacy that was excluded from all mechanistic explanations of artistic crafts.

As for the quantum synthesizer with the classical speaker, the question of aesthetic value could be reduced to whether the formal representation of sound as a quantum state a fruitful approach to explore musical formations. No quantum state is outputted from the system, and any expansion (via super position) of classical sound would be reduced to any of the output compose it, and therefore introducing a sort of random modulation on the music generated.

In the light of our analysis of the previous realizations, we would avoid using random modulation to merely promising element in classical synthesizers (the color of sound as an intriguing example), but rather look to generate quantum states of sound whose superposition could be considered to exist in nature, and participate in the process of music generation or perception. The superposition would be measured, and the output of the measurement would be fed to the classical speaker.

7 Quantum Uncertainty Modulator

Before revealing the structure of the algorithm, we would clearly describe what hypnotized quantum behavior of sound we are trying to capture. Assuming that a signal with a well-defined frequency is a natural state of a signal, Which constitute a basis of states (an observable) that could be measured by an appropriate frequency measurement. Assuming as well that the same holds for time measurement- locating the arrival of a certain signal. The accuracy of measurement of one dictates the accuracy of the measurement of the other, as a necessary outcome of the energy-time uncertainty.¹⁰ When performing a consecutive measurement of one after the other- if both measurements aimed at accuracy under the threshold permitted by the uncertainty relation- the second measurement will destroy the accuracy of the first and push it back to a superposition.

In implementing such mechanism in a system with classical output (classical speakers), which cannot directly reproduce the mechanism of altering the state of the sound by measuring it, we are anyway free from direct physical constraints, and therefore allow choosing the constant of the minimum certainty of time and frequency - marked from now in x .

$$8. \quad \Delta T \Delta f \geq x$$

The constant x would be the modulable parameter in our algorithm. Its initial value would be arbitrarily set to 0.025 (5% frequency determination for half a temporal cycle- as reported in literature over sound discrimination in the human ear [18]).

⁸ Since otherwise brakes causality.

⁹ Only given non commuting observables- holding an uncertainty relation between them, the quantum state is distinguished from a

state of ignorance- as it is in any bell witness.

¹⁰ Assuming that the energy of the sound signal would be as that of the phonon, and so proportional to its frequency.

The Algorithm would be fed with one sound sample- whether of a single frequency or a complex musical sample, with a defined temporal duration- marked as T, and the temporal location of this sound inside a musical piece- marked as $t_{location}$. Though the actual accuracy of its Fourier decomposition is expected to be far higher, we would define the frequency resolution to be the inverse of the duration of our elementary sound sample (based on the golden rule of sampling [19]):

$$9. \Delta f = \frac{1}{T}$$

Once defined as the certainty of momentum of the elementary sound, the uncertainty in time must not violate equation 8, and therefore is set to:

$$10. \Delta T \geq T * x$$

This uncertainty in time is implemented over the sound by altering the time of arrival. The distinct value $t_{location}$ is penalized into a superposition of a Gaussian function form (with respect to Gabor function for elementary signal [5]), centered around $t_{location}$ and with width of ΔT , such that the new probability of this sound to be in a certain time t' is:

$$11. P(t = t') = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\Delta T^2}} e^{-\frac{(t'-t_{location})^2}{\Delta T^2}}$$

We will represent this superposition with discrete 2 level qubits- I.E in a quantum gate computer- where the number of qubits is finite and equal n. As a result, we would only be able to represent 2^n possible temporal locations, with interval of $dt = \frac{\Delta T}{2^n}$.

for convenience we would set $t_{location} = 0$. The quantum state for the temporal location would yield:

$$13. |t_{location}\rangle = \sum_{i=0}^{2^n-1} \sqrt{P\left(\frac{\Delta T}{2} - dt * i\right)} |i\rangle$$

As stated before, the connection of our algorithm to an output classical speaker demands a classical sound to be outputted, and therefore the super position of time location must be measured. The output of the measurement would be the time delay (before or after its original temporal location) In which the sound would be fed to the speaker.

Figure 7: The operation of the quantum uncertainty modulator (lower part) with comparison to an actual quantum measurement (upper part)

To conclude, the action of the algorithm is the following:

1. a sound is being fed into a quantum computer- where only it's temporal duration and location are considered.
2. from the temporal duration an effective frequency uncertainty is determined.
3. the effective frequency uncertainty, along with the modulable constant X, stretch the temporal location of a sound from a distinct location into a normal distribution (Gaussian function).
4. the normal distribution is measured, and a new temporal location is assigned to the sound.

To state clearly, the offset from the input temporal location is dependent on the duration size of the sound- the larger it is (the higher the resolution possible of its frequency pattern and) the higher the possible offset could be. It is in the hand of the musician to choose whether to feed the algorithm with short duration sounds- whose frequency should be harder to identify by the listener, and therefore it's temporal location would be rather stable, or long sounds whose location be unstable. Just as he could vary the constant X for larger and smaller offsets.

We have explicitly omitted from our consideration the actual uncertainty of frequency inside the unit sound- whose information don't arrive to the quantum computer. By that, we give the musician the freedom to declare the elementary sound unit by its musical meaning in the piece. The uncertainty relation is borrowed by analogy to the realm of elementary meaningful sounds. One elementary sound is thought to own one effective frequency, and just as our algorithm choose to realize the certainty of this effective frequency from the sound duration, one can choose alternative approaches- for example one that assign higher certainty of frequency to resolve chords and lower for unresolved ones. In our approach, the longer this effective frequency is appearing, the more precisely a listener with a "musical" measurement device could identify the effective frequency, and therefore the bigger the uncertainty of its time location.

We have also ignored the actual uncertainty in time, dictated by the resolution of our quantum measurement. To follow the analogy in the previous paragraph, an adequate implementation would output a super position of the elementary sound in different times. To continue our analogy, the additional measurement should have altered the effective frequency certainty, from which- for simplicity reasons, we wish to avoid. We hope that the random selection of one of the intended superposition of temporal locations would provide - for the multiple samples produced in one musical piece- a depth resembling that of the actual super position.

As in the analysis of last chapter, the success of this algorithm would be in producing aesthetically meaningful modulations. Musicians are encouraged to experiment with all the range of modulation this algorithm offers, regardless of the physical reality this algorithm is set to mimic. Only once an aesthetic value would be found- if such modulation would offer an appealing randomized rhythm – the modulated uncertainty constant and elementary sound chosen would advocate for an underlining physical process of the same form.

8 Summary

In this article we have discussed various ways to represent music via quantum states. After which we have discussed 3 physical realizations of systems generating music in a quantum state, and what are the physical conditions to be met, for the quantum state to preserve its non-classical behavior all the way to perception by a human listener. Our discussion over the aesthetic value to be expected by any of those machines led us to the underline hypothesis- the success of quantum approach to music relies on the relation between quantum phenomena and the experience of music in general. And therefore, in utilizing the unique logic of quantum computation for music, we choose to highlight a mechanism that if exist in nature would enable quantum phenomena to arrive to the senses. In the premature state of quantum music and quantum sound, our approach is as valid as quantum modulation of sound in a physically meaningless way. It is only the success of aesthetic production, that would encourage extensive research of the relation between music and quantum mechanics.

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